

Supplementary Information

Title: *Integrative taxonomy and mitogenome characterization of the root-knot nematode
Meloidogyne silvestris*

Authors: Justus Aisu, Gerrit Karssen, Daniel Apolonio Silva De Oliveira

*Corresponding author: Justus Aisu, Email: Justus.aisu@idiv.de

Fig. S1. Light micrographs of *Meloidogyne silvestris*. (a–b) Pharyngeal region of second-stage juveniles (J2). (c) Tail region of a second-stage juvenile (J2). (d) Perineal pattern of an adult female.

c)

d)

Fig. S2 | MAFFT alignment of *M. silvestris* 18S rDNA (a), 28S rDNA (b), cox1 (c), and cox2 (d) barcode sequences from specimens of two populations. The sequence alignments showed 99.9% and 99.7% similarity for the 18S and 28S regions, respectively, and 100% similarity for both cox1 and cox2 targeted regions.

Table S1 GenBank accession numbers of mitochondrial genomes included in the phylogenetic analyses.

Nematode species	GenBank accession number
<i>Meloidogyne arenaria</i>	KP202350
<i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>	KJ476150
<i>Meloidogyne silvestris</i>	
<i>Meloidogyne enterolobii</i>	KP202351
<i>Meloidogyne graminicola</i>	NC024275
<i>Meloidogyne incognita</i>	KJ476151
<i>Meloidogyne javanica</i>	KP202352
<i>Meloidogyne oryzae</i>	MK507908
<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>	GQ332424
<i>Heterodera glycines</i>	HM640930
<i>Radopholus similis</i>	NC013253
<i>Bursaphelenchus mucronatus</i>	GU177865
<i>Xiphinema americanum</i>	AY382608
<i>Xiphinema paciatum</i>	NC033870
<i>Pratylenchus vulnus</i>	GQ332425
<i>Ascaris lumbricoides</i>	HQ704900
<i>Ascaris suum</i>	HQ704901
<i>Caenorhabditis briggsae</i>	NC_009885
<i>Cucullanus robustus</i>	GQ332426
<i>Enterobius vermicularis</i>	EU281143
<i>Haemonchus contortus</i>	EU346694
<i>Heterorhabditis bacteriophora</i>	EF043402
<i>Hexameris agrotis</i>	EF368011
<i>Pristionchus pacificus</i>	JF414117
<i>Steinernema carpocapsae</i>	AY591323
<i>Thaumamermis cosgrovei</i>	DQ520857
<i>Trichinella spiralis</i>	AF293969
<i>Wellcomia siamensis</i>	GQ332427
<i>Ascaridia galli</i>	JX624728
<i>Strongyloides stercoralis</i>	AJ558163
<i>Baylisascaris procyonis</i>	JF951366
<i>Trichuris suis</i>	GU070737
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	NC_001328
<i>Lithobius forficatus</i>	NC_002629
<i>Limulus polyphemus</i>	NC_003057

Table S2. Comparative mitochondrial genome PCGs length (bp) of *M. silvestris* and other published *Meloidogyne* species.

	PCGs Length (bp)							
PCGs	<i>M. javanica</i>	<i>M. incognita</i>	<i>M. arenaria</i>	<i>M. enterolobii</i>	<i>M. chitwoodi</i>	<i>M. graminicola</i>	<i>M. oryzae</i>	<i>M. silvestris</i>
cox1	1522	1522	1522	1522	1521	1554	1513	1545
nad1	850	850	850	850	841	885	850	945
nad2	802	802	802	805	807	807	807	810
cox3	762	762	762	760	778	771	771	777
nad6	399	399	399	399	399	390	390	396
nad4L	237	237	237	237	237	246	240	237
cox2	693	693	693	675	661	675	648	684
nad3	315	315	315	315	315	306	312	324
cob	1015	1015	1015	1021	1032	1035	1035	1083
nad4	1173	1173	1173	1173	1164	1170	1167	1212
atp6	552	552	552	552	549	537	522	507
nad5	1474	1474	1474	1480	1470	1503	1464	1533

